

TEACHING SUBJECT-RELATED COMPETENCIES TO STUDENTS IN SOLVING CHEMISTRY PROBLEMS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the development of students' subject-related competencies in solving chemistry problems during lessons.*

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INTRODUCTION. The globalization of education and the introduction of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the teaching and learning process contribute to improving the quality of education in educational institutions. It is known that any technology is based on principles that shape the new content of education. The main subjects of modern education are teachers and students, and their collaborative activities ensure a deep understanding of theoretical and practical knowledge on a given topic.

LITERATURE REVIEW. Education is one of the most complex lifelong activities of a person. The goal of this activity is to assimilate specific information, actions, and behavioral patterns. Education consists of the following components [1]:

- Acquisition of information about the essential properties of the external world necessary for successfully organizing a specific type of ideal or practical activity (knowledge).
- Mastering the ways to use this information for correctly selecting and controlling the methods and processes that correspond to a given task and goal (skills).
- Assimilation of the methods and processes that form the foundation of all these types of activities (competence).

In developing these characteristics in students, it is necessary to integrate subject knowledge, skills, and abilities into the lesson process while also fostering competencies.

Competency-based learning is an educational approach aimed at enabling students to apply the acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities in their personal, professional, and social activities.

Competency-based learning fosters independence, active citizenship, initiative, the ability to use media resources and information and communication technologies effectively, conscious career choice, healthy competition, and general cultural skills in students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS. The knowledge students acquire in subjects such as mathematics, geometry, physics, biology, and others is crucial for them to independently solve chemical problems and exercises. When organizing chemistry lessons in schools and academic lyceums, in addition to the requirements set by the State Educational Standards (DTS), it is essential to ensure that students can also effectively solve test problems and exercises used in university entrance exams.

Based on the above thoughts, we present both typical and atypical chemical problems and their solution methods.

Problem 1:

When 10 moles of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ dissociate, 16 moles of NO_3^- ions are formed. Find the degree of dissociation.

Solution: First, we write the dissociation equation for $Zn(NO_3)_2$. It is known that intermediate salts dissociate completely. $Zn(NO_3)_2 \rightleftharpoons Zn^{2+} + 2NO_3^-$

1. From this equation, it is clear that 1 mole of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ produces 2 moles of NO_3^- ions. Based on this, we set up a proportion:

$$\begin{array}{l} 1 \text{ mol } Zn(NO_3)_2 \text{ ----- } 2 \text{ mol } NO_3^- \\ x \text{ mol ----- } 16 \text{ mol } NO_3^- \end{array}$$

$$x = \frac{1 \cdot 16}{2} = 8$$

2. That is, we found that 8 moles of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ have dissociated. Using this information, we can determine the degree of dissociation. We will use proportions:

$$\begin{array}{l} 10 \text{ mol } Zn(NO_3)_2 \text{ ----- } 100\% \\ 8 \text{ mol } Zn(NO_3)_2 \text{ ----- } x\% \end{array}$$

$$x = \frac{8 \cdot 100}{10} = 80$$

$$\alpha = \frac{n}{N} \cdot 100 = \frac{8}{10} \cdot 100 = 80$$

Answer: The degree of dissociation is 80%, meaning that 80% of the zinc nitrate has dissociated.

This problem can also be interpreted using an unconventional method: Based on the graph showing the dissociation of $Zn(NO_3)_2$, determine its degree of dissociation (%).

Now, the student should be able to analyze the problem by looking at the graph and applying logical reasoning. The graph requires logical knowledge from the student.

Solution: Zinc sulfate is considered a strong electrolyte. Its dissociation is represented as follows:

- It can be seen that, upon dissociation, the number of anions is twice that of the cations, and the number of cations is equal to the amount of dissociated salt. From the graph, it is clear that 16 moles of NO_3^- have been produced, and initially, there were 10 moles of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ salt. The amount of dissociated salt can be determined from the amount of anions formed.

$$x \text{ mol} \text{ --- } 16 \text{ mol}$$

$$1 \text{ mol} \quad 2 \text{ mol}$$

$$x = \frac{1 \cdot 16}{2} = 8$$

So, 8 moles of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ dissociated.

2. To find the degree of dissociation, we use the following formula:

$$\begin{array}{l} 10 \text{ mol } Zn(NO_3)_2 \text{ ----- } 100\% \\ 8 \text{ mol } Zn(NO_3)_2 \text{ ----- } x\% \end{array}$$

$$x = \frac{8 \cdot 100}{10} = 80$$

$$\alpha = \frac{n}{N} \cdot 100 = \frac{8}{10} \cdot 100 = 80$$

Answer: The degree of dissociation is 80%, or 80% of zinc sulfate dissociated.

2nd Problem: Based on the Venn diagram, we need to determine the unique and common properties of the given substances.

Solution: To solve this problem, the student must have sufficient theoretical knowledge about the properties of the given substances. In addition, the student should be able to decipher the riddle presented in the diagram. The first circle represents sulfur dioxide (SO_2), the second circle represents carbon dioxide (CO_2), and the overlapping area between the two circles represents the properties common to both oxides. The available answer choices are as follows:

A) I - it burns in oxygen; II - it is produced by the combustion of glycine; III - the hybridization degree of the central atom is +4;

B) I - the oxidation state of the central atom is +4; II - it is produced by the combustion of cysteine; III - it burns in oxygen;

C) I - the crystal lattice is molecular; II - the oxidation state of the central atom is +4; III - the molecule is linear;

D) I - the oxidation state of the central atom is +4; II - at normal conditions, it occupies a volume of 22.4 liters; III - the molecule contains a metal atom;

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION. The methods of solving are the same, but presenting the problem in different ways is important for reinforcing the theoretical knowledge gained by students. Therefore, the use of unconventional problems and exercises related to the topics in the curriculum and those created by test developers is significant in shaping students' knowledge and skills. It helps increase their logical thinking, develop their competencies, and also enables them to connect the knowledge they acquired from other subjects to chemistry while solving such problems.

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